

Multimodal investigation into the interaction of Quinacrine with microcavity supported lipid bilayers.

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Abstract

Quinacrine is a versatile drug widely recognized for its antimalarial activity by inhibiting of the phospholipase enzyme. It also has anti-anthelmintic and anti-protozoan activities, and is a strong DNA binder that may be used to combat multi-drug resistance in cancer. Despite extensive cell studies, a detail understanding of quinacrine's influence on the cell membrane, including permeability, binding, and rearrangement at the molecular level is lacking. Herein, we apply microcavity suspended lipid bilayers (MSLBs) as *in vitro* models of the cell membrane comprising DOPC, DOPC:Chol(3:1), and DOPC:SM: Chol(2:2:1) to investigate the influence of cholesterol and intrinsic phase heterogeneity induced by mixed lipid composition on membranal interactions of quinacrine. Using electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) and surface enhanced Raman spectroscopy (SERS) as label-free surface sensitive techniques, we have studied quinacrine interaction and permeability across the different MSLBs. Our EIS data reveal that the drug is permeable through ternary DOPC:SM: Chol and DOPC-only bilayer compositions. In contrast, the binary cholesterol/DOPC membrane arrested permeation, yet the drug binds/intercalates at the membrane as reflected by an increase in membrane impedance. SERS supported the EIS data, which was utilized to gain structural insights into the drug membrane interaction. Our SERS data also provides a simple but powerful label-free assessment of drug permeation, since significant SERS enhancement of the drug Raman signature was only observed if the drug accesses the plasmonic interior of the pore cavity passing through the membrane. Fluorescent lifetime correlation spectroscopy (FLCS) provides further biophysical insight, revealing that quinacrine binding increases the lipid diffusivity of DOPC and the ternary membrane while remarkably decreasing the lipid diffusivity of the DOPC:Chol membrane. Overall, because of its adaptability to multimodal approaches, the

MSLB platform provides rich and detailed insights into drug membrane interactions, making it a powerful tool for *in vitro* drug screening.

1. Introduction

Quinacrine, (Scheme 1a) is a drug with multiple therapeutic activities. Used as an antimalarial drug for nearly a century, it is currently under investigation as a cancer chemotherapeutic.¹ Its antimalarial efficacy is due to its action as a beta-hematin inhibitor which results in increased levels of free hemozoin, that triggers oxidative stress via peroxidase reactions, eventually stopping proteolysis and causing damage to the parasite's membrane.^{2,3} Quinacrine has more recently shown significant promise as an anticancer agent.^{4,5} It is a potent Ca²⁺ channel blocker,⁶ it inhibits tumorigenesis in endometrial cancer (EC)⁷, and induces p53, a tumor suppressor protein whilst inhibiting NFκB signaling, resulting in antitumor activity.⁸ Furthermore, recent studies on quinacrine have shown that it binds to and intercalates with DNA.^{1,9} It has thus been repurposed as a chemotherapeutic drug, namely for gynecological malignancies,¹⁰ lung cancer,¹¹ and is currently undergoing phase 2 clinical trial in the treatment of prostate, lung, and colorectal cancer.

Quinacrine is lipophilic, thus likely to interact strongly with the plasma membrane. In a parallel artificial membrane permeation assay (PAMPA), quinacrine was shown to be permeable to the blood-brain barrier (BBB) lipid composition.^{12,13} Such assays although limited in terms of structural mimicry of the biological membrane have been shown to provide a fair correlation with cell permeability.^{14,15}

It has been reported that antimalarial drugs including quinacrine, encapsulated within dendritic micelles are delivered to *Plasmodium*-infected red blood cells (pRBCs).¹⁶ In the absence of specific receptor binding sites, studies have shown that quinacrine has limited interaction with zwitterionic phosphocholine (PC) lipid membrane, but it binds avidly to acidic phosphatidylglycerol (PG) phospholipids.¹⁷ A concerted method in which quinacrine binds first to the phospholipid membrane (mainly phosphatidylglycerol, PG), and then intercalates into the membrane, inhibiting the activity of phospholipase A2 (PLA2)¹⁷ has been hypothesized. Goodman et al. reported evidence of direct interaction of quinacrine with erythrocyte and platelet membrane phospholipids.¹⁸ In addition, the binding between lipid and quinacrine has been reported found to block *Torpedo* nicotinic acetylcholine receptor at the lipid-protein interface.^{19,20}

Despite quinacrine's therapeutic versatility and a variety of intriguing pharmacokinetic properties, details of its interactions with the lipid bilayer and the role of membrane physicochemical properties such as membrane fluidity and the presence of phase-separated heterogeneous domains mimicking mammalian cells have not been studied to date for this drug. A molecular-level understanding of drug-membrane interaction and drug permeability through membranes in a realistic biomimetic lipid bilayer model may provide crucial insights on potential passive permeability for drug screening, before moving on to more expensive cell-based studies. In this regard, we investigate herein the role of membrane composition in quinacrine-membrane binding and permeability utilizing surface sensitive methods on a microcavity-supported lipid bilayer. Our goal is not only to show how different membrane compositions impact drug binding and permeability, but also to demonstrate the potential of a microcavity supported lipid membrane platform as a physiologically mimetic device for *in vitro* drug-membrane interaction testing.

So far, the parallel artificial membrane permeability assay (PAMPA)²¹ and the immobilized artificial membrane (IAM)²² have been two of the most frequent and relatively easy *in vitro* approaches for the passive mode of small molecule drug permeability across cell membrane test. Although both have proved to be reliable, their biomimicry is limited since neither represents a true bilayer with a hydrophobic core and reflects the actual thickness and asymmetry of the plasma membrane bilayer. Microcavity-supported lipid bilayer may offer a useful, low-cost alternative for studying drug interactions with the membrane during the early stages of drug development.²³ Previously *in vitro* platforms have been used to anticipate passive membrane permeability and membrane-associated toxicological problems isolated from the complexity of the living cell.^{24,25} Biomembrane models, such as liposomes, and supported lipid bilayers (SLB), have been successfully applied to interrogate the interaction of membrane lipids with small molecules.²⁶⁻³¹ They have provided much insight, but there is still room for improvement in the biomimicry of the *in vivo* membrane. In the case of liposomes they are limited to interfacial studies at two dimensions, whilst interference from the interfacial support due to pinning on the fluidity and functionality of the bilayer and associated proteins limits SLB biomimicry.³²⁻³⁵ Several modifications have been developed that may decouple the proximal leaflet from the substrate while retaining membrane component mobility. These include tethered lipid bilayer membranes and cushioned bilayer membranes.³⁶⁻⁴¹ The advantage of SLB based approaches is that they are more amenable to experimental interrogation than liposomes.⁴²⁻⁴⁶ In particular, when the solid support is a conducting metal

electrode, it can be used for both electrochemical and vibrational spectroscopic studies as a label-free approach, providing diverse insights on the biophysical aspect of drug-membrane interaction at the molecular level.

Alternative approaches that build membranes supported over aqueous micro pores to improve the fluidity without the use of tethers while maintaining stability have evolved. Most importantly, in the case of buffer filled pore suspended bilayers, they offer the advantage of a relatively deep aqueous reservoir in contact with the proximal leaflet, which SLBs do not have.⁴⁷⁻⁵² We recently reported on such microcavity array supported lipid bilayers (MSLBs) made from polystyrene sphere templated gold and PDMS substrates, which we used to explore drug-membrane⁵³⁻⁵⁶ and protein-membrane⁵⁷⁻⁵⁹ interactions.

Herein, using multimodal detection methods, we investigate how quinacrine interacts with three distinct bilayer compositions, DOPC, DOPC:Chol(3:1), and DOPC:SM:Chol(2:2:1). The first two representing fluidic liquid disordered phases, with and without cholesterol to investigate the influence of cholesterol on permeability of such a phase and a ternary composition known to form both liquid disordered and ordered phases. Previously, it was shown that the heterogeneity caused by the long acyl chain of SM might improve drug permeability by encouraging polar contact.^{60,61} Thus, the membrane compositions explored were selected on the basis of their different membrane homogeneity and fluidity to understand how these factors influence quinacrine interaction.⁶²⁻⁶⁵ We used electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) as a label-free and surface-sensitive technique that can detect drug binding, permeation and thickness change by measuring the membrane admittance. Fluorescence lifetime correlation spectroscopy (FLCS) was used to understand any drug-induced lipid mobility changes. And molecular structural insights on quinacrine-membrane interactions are obtained from surface enhanced Raman spectroscopy by exploiting the plasmonic properties of the gold microcavity pore array.

2. Experimental Section

Materials: 1,2-Dioleoyl-*sn*-glycerophosphocholine (DOPC), and N-(octadecanoyl)-sphing-4-enine-1-phosphocholine (SM) in powder form were purchased from Avanti polar lipids (Instruchemie, The Netherlands). Cholesterol and quinacrine of high purity (>99%) were obtained from Sigma-Aldrich (Wicklow, Ireland), and were used as purchased. 1,2-dioleoyl-*sn*-glycero-3-phosphoethanolamine labeled ATTO655 (DOPE-ATTO655) was purchase from ATTO-TEC GmbH (Siegen, Germany). Polydimethylsiloxane silicon elastomer (PDMS) was

purchased from Dow Corning GmbH (Wiesbaden, Germany). Gold disk electrodes consisting of silicon wafers coated with a 100 nm layer of gold on a 50 Å layer of titanium adhesive were obtained from AMS Biotechnology Inc. Monodisperse polystyrene latex spheres were obtained from Bangs Laboratories Inc. The commercial cyanide free gold plating solution (TG-25 RTU) was obtained from Technic Inc. All other HPLC grade reagents were obtained from Sigma-Aldrich and used as obtained. Ultra-pure water with a resistivity 18.2 MΩcm was produced by a Milli-Q (Millipore Academic) system and used for buffer preparation.

Methods. *Fabrication of gold microcavity array:* Gold microcavity array electrodes were prepared by polystyrene (PS) microsphere lithographic techniques as reported previously.^{53,55,57,66} In brief, 100 nm gold coated silicon wafer electrodes (Platypus technologies, USA) of $\sim 1 \times 1$ cm² were cut and cleaned by washing with THF followed by ethanol then dried under gentle stream of HP N₂. The electrodes were then plasma treated for 5 mins to render the surface hydrophilic. After plasma treatment, 1% (v/v) of PS spheres (1 μm diameter) were drop cast over the gold chip and allowed to spread uniformly across the whole area. The chip was left overnight without shaking in order to evaporate the solvent to form a hexagonally close packed self-assembled microsphere array. Next, controlled electrochemical deposition of gold was carried using a well characterised amperometric I-t curve that can be used to determine precisely when gold is ~ 0.5 μm thickness⁶⁷ using a 3-electrode electrochemical workstation (Fig. S1a, SI). After gold deposition, the substrates were rinsed with water and subsequently electrochemically cleaned using 0.05 M H₂SO₄ using cyclic voltammetry (Fig. S1b, SI) in order to remove any oxide layers formed. After cleaning, the substrate was rinsed with Milli-Q water, dried under N₂, and soaked for at least 48 hrs in an ethanolic solution of 1 mM 6-Mercapto-1-hexanol (MH) to form self-assembled monolayer (SAM). As described previously, the PS spheres were permitted to remain in place to act as a template preventing the MH SAM assembling at the pore interior, limiting the SAM to the interstitial planar regions at the top surface of the array between pores.^{43,57} The chemical modification of the substrate in the MH treatment step improves the stability of the bilayer by promoting the wettability of gold substrate with an –OH functionalized interface. After SAM formation, the substrates were washed with ethanol to remove any unbound thiol and further soaked in THF for 5 mins. This step results in the complete removal of PS spheres leaving periodic micropore arrays with pore diameters of 1 μm and 0.5 μm depth with SAM at the interstitial planar regions. After microcavity array fabrication, the cavities were washed with

ethanol 2-3 times and subsequently rinsed 8-10 times with milli-Q water and the substrate is submerged in PBS buffer for at least 24 hrs before using for MSLB preparation.

Fabrication of PDMS microcavity array: The arrays were prepared in PDMS for optical studies. Mica sheets of a few micrometers thicknesses were cut to $\sim 1 \times 1$ cm² dimensions and glued to glass cover slides. To form PS array over the mica surface, ~ 50 μ L of ethanolic solution of 0.1% of 4.61 μ m PS was drop cast onto the flat mica surface. After ethanol evaporation, PDMS was poured onto the PS assembled at the mica sheet and cured at 90 °C for 1h. After cooling, the PDMS was removed gently to reveal the PS array within a thin chamber of identical dimensions provided by the mica sheet thickness, which was suitable for confocal imaging and spectroscopy.^{53,68} The microcavity array was then formed by dissolving the PS sphere template from the PDMS substrate in tetrahydrofuran (THF) for 15 min via sonication. The substrates were then left to dry overnight. The resulting PDMS cavity arrays were hexagonally packed, and the pore diameter, determined by atomic force microscopy was ~ 2 μ m (Fig. S1c, SI). The PDMS substrates were plasma cleaned using oxygen plasma for 5 min to make the surface hydrophilic and the microcavities were buffer filled by sonication and stored inside buffer for further use.

Preparation of microcavity spanned bilayer membranes: A combination of Langmuir-Blodgett (LB) and vesicle fusion (VF) methods were employed respectively for assembly of the proximal and distal leaflet of lipid bilayers over buffer filled gold and PDMS microcavity array according to a slight modification of a previously reported method^{43,68}. In brief, for Langmuir-Blodgett transfer, either single or multicomponent lipid mixtures were first dissolved in chloroform (~ 1 mg/mL) and then ~ 50 μ L of lipid solutions were added to the Langmuir trough, KN2006 (KSV-NIMA technology). A lag time of 10 mins was set before compressing and decompressing (4 cycles) the monolayers below the collapse surface pressure, and then the monolayers are held at a constant surface pressure of 33 mN/m for 5 min. The submerged gold/PDMS cavity array substrates in the LB trough were withdrawn from the water surface vertically at a speed of 5 mm/min to form the proximal leaflet of the bilayer. For vesicle preparation, the lipid solution (1 mg/mL) was dried in a 1.5 mL glass vial under the gentle stream of N₂ gas to form a thin film. The dried lipid films were rehydrated in 1 mL of 0.01 M phosphate buffer saline (PBS), pH 7.4 and vortexed for a period of 30-60 s. Next, the lipid suspensions were extruded 11 times through a 100 nm polycarbonate filter using a mini-extruder (Avanti Polar Lipids) to form large unilamellar vesicles (LUV) that were then diluted to a final concentration of 0.25 mg/mL. The monolayer modified cavity array was then

submerged in the solutions of vesicle for 1 hr to allow them to fuse and form the MSLB. Next, the bilayer is gently washed with excess PBS buffer to remove any unfused vesicles, the process was carried out in such a way that at no point during the process are the bilayers were exposed to air.

Electrochemical Impedance Spectroscopy, EIS: The electrochemical measurements were performed with a CH760A potentiostat (CH Instruments, USA). A standard 3-electrode cell comprised of gold microcavity suspended bilayer as working electrode, an Ag/AgCl (1M KCl) reference electrode and a platinum wire auxiliary electrode. The EIS data were measured over a frequency range of 0.05 to 10^5 Hz with an ac modulation amplitude of 0.01 V at a potential DC bias of 0 V (vs Ag/AgCl). All measurements were carried out in a glass cell (approximate volume of 4 mL) in contact with PBS buffer maintained at pH 7.4. The EIS of the aqueous filled microcavity array coated with the lipid bilayer was measured initially prior to the addition of drugs to ensure signal stability. The non-Faradaic EIS signal from the MSLBs was evaluated for stability and it was found that when initially placed in contact with the PBS buffer at 0V an initial fluctuation of resistance is seen that stabilizes within an hour and then remains unchanged over a prolonged window (10-12 hrs). This 10 hrs window of stability is well beyond our experimental time window (3-4 hrs) for drug binding studies. A time lag of 60-90 mins was allowed for each membrane composition to ensure it had equilibrated in the electrochemical cell (no fluctuation of EIS) before drug solutions were titrated. The electrochemical impedance response of the lipid bilayer was then measured for each drug concentration (0-20 μ M). Each measurement takes approximately 4 min and was carried out at room temperature (22 ± 1 °C). The measured data were analysed using Z-View software with an equivalent circuit fitting model (ECM) (Scheme 1c) as described earlier^{55,56}, to estimate the membrane resistivity and capacitance values before and after drug interaction. The circuit consists of a parallel combination of solution resistance (R_s) and capacitor in series with a parallel combination of constant phase element, CPE (C_{array}) and a cavity resistive elements (R_{array}) of the microcavity array, and the membrane is approximated by a resistive element (R_M) in parallel with a CPE (Q_M). A Constant Phase Element (CPE) is used in the equivalent circuit instead of pure capacitors as the impedance of solid electrodes usually deviates from pure capacitor due to microscopic chemical inhomogeneity on both the electrode surface and the lipid bilayer. Depending on the composition, as described below, from EIS the bilayer resistance for an intact bilayer ranges be from 2 to 10 M Ω (compared to k Ω resistance of SAM modified cavity array prior to bilayer deposition. We have previously shown that this resistance

range corresponds to an intact SLB and so used the resistance values to validate the bilayer prior to measurement.^{53,56} Poorly formed bilayers tended to show lower resistance and were discarded.⁵⁶

Surface Enhanced Raman Spectroscopy (SERS) measurements: The gold microcavity supported lipid bilayers in contact with PBS, pH 7.4 studied by Raman spectroscopy, using a confocal microscope (HORIBA, UK) equipped with the LabSpec software, LabSpec 5.45.09. 785 nm, was used for excitation through a pinhole of 100 μM equipped for dispersion grating with 1200 grooves/mm. For both excitation and detection a 50X (air, NA:0.75) objective was used. The spectra were collected across a 200-3400 cm^{-1} spectral range using 1% laser power (0.1 mW), to avoid plasmonic heating that can damage the bilayer. An exposure time of 4s and accumulation number 6 s was used for spectral recording. The instrument was calibrated using Si (100) wafer calibrated to its standard peak 520.7 cm^{-1} and the Rayleigh line before measurement of the sample. The spectra of bulk materials, powder form of lipid or drug (~2 mg), were collected from a flat gold substrate at high laser power of 100 mW versus 0.1 mW for SERS measurements at MSLB platform.

Scheme 1. a) Chemical structure a) and b) DFT (CAM-B3LYP) optimized structure of quinacrine: grey: carbon, white: hydrogen, green: chlorine, red: oxygen and blue: nitrogen. For clarity double bonds are not displayed. c) Schematic representation of gold microcavity suspended lipid bilayer (MSLB) array used in this work (not to scale) for dual detection using EIS and SERS method: On the right, the equivalent circuit model (ECM) model used herein to fit EIS data. In the ECM, R_{el} , and C_{array} represents solution electrolyte resistance and stray

capacitance, R_M and Q_M represent respectively as membrane resistance and constant phase element (CPE), and R_{array} and Q_{array} are the microcavity array resistance and CPE. d) Schematic representation of PDMS microcavity based microfluidic device (*top*) for fluorescent lifetime imaging and FCS study. The bright round shape (*bottom left*) shown in the reflectance image corresponds to the aqueous filled cavities and (*bottom right*) shows the corresponding fluorescent lifetime image in the same area obtained from DOPC MSLB doped with 0.01 mol% of fluorescently labelled lipid probe, DOPE-ATTO655. The dark regions in the reflectance image are the cavities where buffer did not fill and accordingly, bright ring-like structures in the FLIM image are unfilled cavities where bilayer failed to span. This distinction meant it was facile to ensure that filled/cavity suspended bilayers were always selected for the study.

Fluorescence Lifetime Correlation Spectroscopy (FLCS): Fluorescence lifetime imaging (FLIM) and fluorescence lifetime correlation spectroscopy (FLCS) measurements were performed using a Microtime 200 system (PicoQuant GmbH, Germany) integrated with FCS module, dual SPD detection unit, time-correlated single photon counting (TCSPC), and inverted microscope model Olympus X1-71 with a Olympus UPlan SApo 60x/1.2 water immersion objective. The FLIM and FLCS measurements were acquired from a PDMS microcavity sandwiched in a microfluidics device, as schematically depicted in Scheme 1d (*top*). A single mode optical fibre guides the lasers to the main unit and provides a homogeneous Gaussian profile excitation beam. The lasers were pulsed at 20 MHz, corresponding to an interval of 50 ns. The emitted fluorescence was collected through the microscope objective and dichroic mirror 635rpc blocked the backscattered light and HQ670lp AHF/Chroma 640 nm filters were used to clean up the signal. A 50 μm pinhole was used. Fluorescence was detected using a single photon avalanche diode (SPAD) from MPD (PicoQuant). The TCSPC enabled simultaneous assessment of the lifetime in a nanosecond range along with the time of diffusion in the millisecond range. Furthermore, TCSPC in life time mode, has the ability to filter out any contribution from after-pulsing, suppress scattered light and parasitic signals from background. Before FCLS measurement, backscattered images of the substrate (images were taken using an OD3 density filter, marked reflectance in Scheme 1d (*bottom left*)) and fluorescent life-time images were acquired to ensure optimal positioning of focus at the buffer filled cavities where the bilayers are spanned (marked FLIM in Scheme 1d (*bottom right*)). FLCS analyzes the time-dependent fluctuations of the fluorescence intensity $\partial I(t)$ recorded over 30 s and conform to an autocorrelation function, $G(t_c) = \langle \partial I(t) \rangle \cdot \langle \partial I(t + t_c) \rangle / \langle \partial I(t) \rangle^2$, where $\langle \rangle$ denotes the time average, and $\langle \partial I(t) \rangle$ and

$\langle \delta I(t + t_c) \rangle$ are the fluorescent intensity fluctuations around the mean value at time, t and $t + t_c$ respectively, where t_c is the lag time. The FLCS autocorrelation data fit to a 2D diffusion model; equation Eq. (1);

$$G(t_c) = \frac{1}{N} \frac{1}{1+(t_c/\tau_D)^\alpha} \quad (1)$$

where, τ_D is the transit time, N is the average lipid probe number, and α is the anomaly coefficient. $G(t_c)$ is autocorrelation measure of the self-similarity of a signal in time, i.e., the overlap of a signal with itself at various lag time t_c . From the fitting the τ_D values were evaluated and accordingly, the diffusion coefficient can be obtained by Eq. (2);

$$D = \frac{\omega^2}{4\tau_D} \quad (2)$$

where ω is the observation beam waist diameter typically obtained from calibration of a standard dye diffusing in 3D with a known diffusion coefficient value.

Results and Discussion

Many medications function intracellularly and thus must first cross the plasma membrane to reach their target. To better understand the drug-membrane interaction and its physicochemical significance in drug action, model lipid bilayers provides a convenient means to isolate the role of membrane from the complexity of the cell. Biomimetic membranes that offer control over composition offer the opportunity to mimic particular aspects of cell membranes such as phase or packing and when combined with multiple interrogation methods can provide deep insight into how the drug and membrane interact. The present work unravels in detail, the interaction of a well-known antimalarial drug, quinacrine, employing multi-modal analytical approaches and a pore supported lipid membrane platform. Using electrochemical impedance, surface-enhanced Raman spectroscopy, fluorescence lifetime imaging, and correlation spectroscopy, we examined the effects of quinacrine on several membranes one at a time and briefly discussed the results obtained by combining results from various approaches near the end.

Studies of quinacrine interaction with membrane using electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS)

Electrodes comprised of periodic pore arrays of 1 μm pore diameter and 0.5 μm depth, prepared as described previously,^{53,55,57} were used to assemble microcavity suspended lipid bilayers

(MSLB) using a combination of the Langmuir-Blodgett and vesicle fusion method. The interaction of quinacrine with pore-suspended bilayers made of simple DOPC membrane was first studied using non-Faradaic electrochemical impedance spectroscopy in PBS buffer. Figure 1 depicts representative non-Faradaic electrochemical impedance spectrum (EIS) responses for DOPC MSLBs before and after quinacrine (20 μ M) addition in PBS. Changes to EIS signal before (open black) and after addition of a fixed concentration of quinacrine (open violet) can be represented by both the Nyquist (Fig. 1a) and complex capacitance (Fig.1b) plots. The corresponding EIS data were fit to the previously described equivalent circuit model (ECM) (Scheme 1c)^{55,56} to provide absolute membrane resistance and capacitance values. With this model, the change in membrane resistance (R_M) and capacitance (Q_M) upon quinacrine addition are significant compared to other components in the ECM circuit. For example, the electrolyte solution resistance ($\sim 35\pm 5 \Omega$), stray capacitance C_{stray} (~ 1 nF) due to the electronics connector, cavity array resistance ($R_{\text{array}} \sim 1$ k Ω), and capacitance ($Q_{\text{array}} \sim 40 \mu\text{F}\cdot\text{s}^{m-1}$, $m=0.5$) remain essentially unchanged. Note that in the ECM model, we employed a constant phase element (CPE) rather than a pure capacitor, since the impedance of gold porous electrodes deviates from flat gold owing to the presence of microscopic inhomogeneities in the electrode surface. The complex capacitance when a CPE is used, can be expressed as $1/(Qj\omega)^m$, where Q is analogous to the magnitude of capacitance, ω is the angular frequency (rad/sec), and m is a homogeneity parameter varying between 0 and 1. $m=1$, for an ideal capacitor, whereas $m=0$ corresponds to a pure resistor. In our model, the m values for CPE at the membrane and array components are $\sim 0.93\pm 0.01$ and 0.5 ± 0.02 respectively, which typically corresponds to the membrane when CPE approaches an ideal capacitor and the array CPE becomes a series RC circuit or Warburg impedance.⁵⁶ Instead of a pure capacitor unit (F), the unit of (Q_M) is stated as $F\cdot\text{s}^{m-1}$. While the capacitance can be obtained from the Q value using the expression, $C(\omega) = Q\omega^{m-1}$, it only valid for a specific ω , limited to the specific ECM and thus is not used in this study. Instead, as previously stated, we quote CPE (Q) as membrane capacitance values.

From Fig. 1, the absolute resistance (R_M) and capacitance (Q_M) values of pristine DOPC membrane (no drug) were found to be 2.58 ± 0.01 M Ω and $5.30\pm 0.02 \mu\text{F}\cdot\text{s}^{m-1}$ respectively. The addition of quinacrine (20 μ M) reduces the R_M to 2.06 ± 0.02 M Ω and the capacitance ($5.28\pm 0.02 \mu\text{F}\cdot\text{s}^{m-1}$) of the membrane. The aforementioned resistance and capacitance measurements have not been normalized to active surface area. This is because during

substrate fabrication, variation in PS sphere packing at the to 1 cm \times 1.2 cm flat gold electrodes causes a variation in electrode area, resulting in around 2-5% fluctuation in electrode area/roughness. Nonetheless, the active surface area of bare cavity array electrodes was \sim 8-10 cm² than that of flat gold electrodes (in the absence of SAM and bilayer). Depending on the membrane composition and the total electroactive area of gold electrodes explored in this work, the absolute value of membrane resistance and capacitance ranges from 20-80 M Ω cm² and 0.4-0.7 μ F \cdot s^{m-1}cm⁻², as calculated by multiplying and dividing by electroactive area. Because SAM selectively modifies top interstitial region of gold cavities, estimating the active surface area in presence of SAM is difficult, we report instead the relative changes in impedance generated by quinacrine. Nevertheless, the absolute values of membrane resistance and capacitance obtained from this work are in agreement with previous reports.^{53,55,69-72}

Figure 1. a) Representative Nyquist plot and b) frequency normalized complex capacitance plot of the DOPC MSLB before (open black) and after 20 μ M quinacrine (open violet) interaction, with their corresponding fit curves (solid lines) using ECM, as illustrated in Scheme 1c. The Bode plot of the DOPC bilayer before drug addition is shown in the inset in (a). EIS measurements were performed in PBS buffer (pH=7.4) for frequencies ranging from 0.5 Hz to 10⁵ Hz at 0 V DC bias potential (versus Ag/AgCl (1 M KCl)) with an AC modulation amplitude of 10 mV. All the measurements were performed at 22 \pm 1 $^{\circ}$ C.

Next, we measured changes in membrane impedance as the concentration of quinacrine in the contact solution changed from 1 to 20 μ M (which is within the physiological concentration

dose limit⁶) (Fig. 2). Each drug concentration was added 10 minutes before measurement to allow for membrane incubation. In order to guarantee the film's quality and stability, the EIS signal was monitored for 10-12 hours prior to drug administration. After adding MSLB to the cell, resistance rises initially and equilibrates in 60-90 minutes depending on membrane composition. The membrane impedance remained stable for 10 to 12 hours after equilibration.^{55,56} The MSLB was rejected when in the absolute resistance dropped below 1 M Ω and capacitance exceeded 10 $\mu\text{F}\cdot\text{s}^{\text{m}^{-1}}$ during an hour of EIS operation. By 30 hours, the resistivity had started to fall from the equilibration, establishing our stability window. Our drug titration experiments were all finished within 3-4 hours, which is well within the window of stability. Prior to drug addition, the absolute membrane resistance of DOPC, DOPC:Chol and DOPC:SM:Chol was 2.58 ± 0.01 , 2.82 ± 0.03 , and 4.49 ± 0.02 M Ω , respectively, consistent with increased membrane ordering due to tighter packing of alkyl chains of lipid tails in presence of cholesterol and SM/Chol. The corresponding capacitance values were respectively, 5.30 ± 0.02 , 4.93 ± 0.22 , and 4.42 ± 0.32 $\mu\text{F}\cdot\text{s}^{\text{m}^{-1}}$. Given the inverse relationship between capacitance and thickness of the dielectric (in this case, lipid bilayer), the result reflects upon increase in membrane complexity the membrane thickness increases.

The Nyquist plot (Fig.2) shows that drug induced response varies with membrane type. For example, with increasing quinacrine concentration at a pure DOPC, the EIS signal shifts towards the real Z' -axis (Fig. 2a), indicating that the drug reduces bilayer impedance. The impedance of the ternary membrane (DOPC:SM:Chol), similarly decreases following drug interaction (Fig. 2c) however the decline is much greater than for DOPC. Increased ion permeation or membrane leakiness is typically linked to reduced lipid bilayer impedance. In contrast, for the DOPC:Chol membrane (Fig. 2b), a modest but systematic increase in impedance is detected that only at the very highest drug concentration, exceeds experimental error.

To investigate recovery of the membrane after drug interaction, we exchanged the drug-containing buffer for blank buffer, and all membranes showed decreased impedance. However whereas DOPC exhibited a very large impedance decline (orange symbols in each panel of Fig.2), a much weaker decline was observed for DOPC:SM:Chol. Consistent with the tighter packing of this membrane and in spite of the apparent weak impact of drug on membrane impedance a measurable impedance decrease was also observed for drug for DOPC:Chol on blank buffer exchange. EIS signals were monitored for 30 minutes after the buffer exchange

but impedance did not recover for the DOPC membrane, indicating that the medication caused irreversible changes to the DOPC membrane.

In the absence of bilayer, i.e. for SAM-only modified cavity array electrodes, adding 10 μM quinacrine to the cell elicited a small increase in resistance (R_{array}) and decrease in capacitance (Q_{array}), possibly implying quinacrine adsorption at the cavity interior (Fig. S2, SI). These alterations occur within 10 minutes of drug addition to the cell and remain unchanged after 6-7 hours. We also observed a decrease in capacitance (Q_{array}) for DOPC and DOPC:SM:Chol MSLB of comparable magnitude but not for DOPC:Chol, indicating quinacrine penetration across the former two membranes followed with a rise in membrane CPE (Q_M).

Figure 2. Non-Faradaic EIS data showing the Nyquist plots obtained from titration of quinacrine into contacting solution at (a) DOPC, (b) DOPC:Chol (3:1) and (c) DOPC:SM:Chol (2:2:1) membrane suspended across gold microcavity array. The experiments were carried out in three-electrode cell configuration, where the MSLB array on gold is the working electrode, Ag/AgCl (1M KCl) is reference, and coiled Pt wire is counter electrode. The electrolyte solution used was 0.01 M PBS solution (pH 7.4). EIS was recorded for frequencies between 0.05 Hz to 10^5 Hz at a DC bias of 0 V with an AC amplitude of 10 mV at 22 ± 1 °C. In each panel, the \square , \circ , Δ , ∇ , \diamond symbols represent 0, 1, 5, 10 and 20 μM quinacrine present in the contact solution, and \triangleleft represents buffer exchange (BE) measurement (following post incubated sample to fresh PBS buffer). The measurements are performed in triplicate for each bilayer type.

Table 1. Relative change in resistance values of different membrane composition after quinacrine titration derived from non-linear least-squares fit using ECM model.

Quinacrine (μM)	ΔR ($\text{M}\Omega$)		
	DOPC	DOPC:Chol	DOPC:SM:Chol
0	0.0	0.0	0.0
1	-0.302 ± 0.02	0.022 ± 0.01	-0.703 ± 0.09
5	-0.47 ± 0.01	0.064 ± 0.00	-1.249 ± 0.13
10	-0.5 ± 0.08	0.097 ± 0.00	-1.915 ± 0.12
20	-0.52 ± 0.09	0.099 ± 0.00	-2.06 ± 0.10
buffer exchange	-2.33 ± 0.18	-0.493 ± 0.02	-2.81 ± 0.15

Table 2. Relative change in capacitance values of different membrane composition after quinacrine titration derived from non-linear least squares fit to the EIS data.

Quinacrine (μM)	ΔQ ($\mu\text{F}\cdot\text{s}^{\text{m}-1}$)		
	DOPC	DOPC:Chol	DOPC:SM:Chol
0	0.0	0.0	0.0
1	0.04 ± 0.01	-0.025 ± 0.01	0.215 ± 0.01
5	0.07 ± 0.02	-0.016 ± 0.02	0.267 ± 0.07
10	-0.05 ± 0.03	-0.023 ± 0.01	0.272 ± 0.05
20	-0.06 ± 0.04	-0.047 ± 0.01	0.328 ± 0.51
buffer exchange	0.13 ± 0.03	0.144 ± 0.018	0.693 ± 0.14

We extracted the absolute membrane resistance and capacitance values before and after drug interaction using the aforementioned ECM. Where in order to get relative changes (Δ), we normalized to pristine membrane's impedance. The relative resistance change (ΔR) is defined as $R_M^0 - R_M^{\text{drug}}$, where R_M^0 and R_M^{drug} is the pristine membrane's resistance without and with the drug and relative change in capacitance (ΔQ) is $Q_M^0 - Q_M^{\text{drug}}$. These values are provided in Tables 1 and 2 respectively..

The relative change in resistance and capacitance values are plotted against quinacrine concentration and displayed in Figs. 3a and b, respectively. The ΔR versus quinacrine concentration data (filled symbol, Fig. 3a) were fit (solid lines, Fig. 3a) iteratively to the empirical Langmuir isotherm model described by equation (3), and the fit parameters of the Langmuir isotherm are provided in Table 3.

$$\Delta R = \frac{\Delta R_{sat}(K_a C)}{1+(K_a C)} \quad (3)$$

where ΔR is the change in membrane resistance, ΔR_{sat} is absorption capacity or saturated binding of the drug, K_a is an empirical association constant, and C is the drug's bulk concentration.^{73,74} As can be seen, as drug concentration increases, membrane resistance for DOPC and DOPC:SM:Chol membranes decreases. And, as previously described, the ternary composition has the biggest influence on membrane resistance; DOPC:SM:Chol (blue, $\Delta R_{sat} = -2.39 \pm 0.24 \text{ M}\Omega$) compared to DOPC (black, $\Delta R_{sat} = -0.536 \pm 0.02 \text{ M}\Omega$) (Fig. 3a). Accordingly, the association constant, K_a values are found to be 0.30 ± 0.01 and $1.27 \pm 0.02 \text{ L}\cdot\mu\text{M}^{-1}$ for DOPC:SM:Chol and DOPC membrane respectively. In contrast, DOPC:Chol (red) with a $\Delta R_{sat} = 0.126 \pm 0.01 \text{ M}\Omega$ membrane showed a very small but non-negligible increase in relative resistance values. The K_a value for DOPC:Chol bilayer was evaluated from the fit and found to be $0.23 \pm 0.07 \text{ L}\cdot\mu\text{M}^{-1}$.

Figure 3. The plot represents the relative change in membrane (a) resistance and (b) capacitance for a designated lipid composition versus quinacrine concentrations. In each panel, the symbols ■, ● and ▲ represent DOPC, DOPC:Chol and DOPC:SM:Chol membrane compositions. In panel (a), solid lines are the best-fit curves to the Langmuir isotherm model according to Eq. (3). Each data point given is a mean value \pm SD and was assessed in triplicate for each bilayer type. The dashed lines in panel b are the lines guide to the eye.

Table 3. Data obtained for quinacrine drug by fitting relative change in resistance of different lipid composition to a non-linear Langmuir isotherm model.

lipid composition	$\Delta R_{\text{sat}}(\text{M}\Omega)$	$K_a(\text{L}\cdot\mu\text{M}^{-1})$	R^2
DOPC	-0.536 \pm 0.01	1.27 \pm 0.02	0.99
DOPC:Chol	0.126 \pm 0.01	0.23 \pm 0.07	0.98
DOPC:SM:Chol	-2.39 \pm 0.24	0.30 \pm 0.01	0.96

Figure 3b illustrates relative change in capacitance (ΔQ) values versus quinacrine concentrations for the three different membrane types. Because, treating the membrane as a parallel plate capacitor, the capacitance is inversely related to membrane thickness, the ΔQ versus concentration plot can reflect alterations to membrane thickness at different quinacrine concentrations. Although DOPC resistance data shows a large rise in membrane permittivity with increasing drug concentration, the membrane thickness remains relatively constant, reflected in only small changes to membrane capacitance (Fig. 3b). Such decreased resistance without accompanying a change in capacitance may indicate pores/ion channels. It is worth noting that DOPC membrane thinning occurs at low drug concentrations (1 and 5 μM), but capacitance then decreases at higher quinacrine concentration attributed to drug accumulation at high drug concentrations (10 and 20 μM) (Fig. 3b).

For DOPC:Chol capacitance, negligible reduction in ΔQ occurred. Conversely, for DOPC:SM:Chol, ΔQ increases considerably in the presence of the drug, indicating membrane thinning. When the drug-containing solution is exchanged with fresh PBS buffer, EIS confirms that the membrane is still intact, as reflected by positive ΔQ values for DOPC:SM:Chol (0.693 \pm 0.14 $\mu\text{F}\cdot\text{s}^{\text{m}^{-1}}$) (cf. Table 2).

Surface enhanced Raman spectroscopy of Membrane-Quinacrine interaction.

As reported previously, gold cavity array structures create excellent SERS (surface enhanced Raman spectroscopy) platforms.^{67,75–77} As a result, we used Raman spectroscopy of the bilayers at the array to gain molecular structural insight into the drug's interaction with the membrane. Before SERS measurements, we first performed classical Raman measurements of the individual lipids; DOPC and cholesterol, and quinacrine drug in their powder form on flat gold substrates. The Raman spectra of DOPC powder control are shown in the bottom panel of Fig. 4a (with characteristic features highlighted in light grey) for comparison with the band position obtained in SERS from DOPC bilayer on MSLBs, as shown in black lines. In all cases, the Raman shift band positions are consistent with the reported literature values for lipids.^{78–82} The main features in the Raman spectra of DOPC are observed in the fingerprint regions of the hydrocarbon chain, and can be ascribed to bending, scissoring, and twisting, and as well as C-C, C-H, and C=C stretching modes. For example, the bands between 1440 and 1650 cm^{-1} are associated with CH_2 scissors bending ($\delta(\text{CH}_2)$) and C=C double bond stretching ($\nu(\text{C}=\text{C})$), respectively. Other prominent features near 1250-1300 and 1025-1140 cm^{-1} correspond to CH_2/CH deformation and C-C backbone single bond stretching, respectively. Bands originating from the phospholipid head can be observed at 718, 876, 957 and 1737 cm^{-1} , assigned to symmetric choline ($\nu_s\text{C}-\text{N}^+-\text{C}$) stretching, antisymmetric choline ($\nu_{\text{as}}\text{C}-\text{N}^+-\text{C}$) stretching, phosphate P-O stretching ($\nu(\text{P}-\text{O})$), and ester carbonyl stretching ($\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$) respectively. The Raman spectrum for quinacrine powder is shown in the top panel (red, Fig. 4a,b). The theoretical Raman spectrum of quinacrine (cf. Scheme 1b for energy minimized structure) was predicted by DFT computation for the orientation averaged spectrum by employing CAM-B3LYP functional using the 6-311++G(d,p) basis set in *Gaussian 09* tool, as reported previously.⁸³ The experimental and theoretical data are in excellent agreement, and band assignment (Fig. S3, SI). The Raman features centred at 1372, 1401 and 1469 cm^{-1} are assigned to in-plane ring stretching vibrations, while the band at 1586 cm^{-1} is assigned to exocyclic C-N stretching mode, and these assignments are in good agreement with previously report Raman data for the drug.⁸⁴

Based on this information, the experimental SERS spectra of DOPC bilayer alone (Fig. 4a, black) and in contact with quinacrine (Fig. 4a, blue) were be compared with the analogous spectra for the DOPC:Chol bilayer. We focussed on this comparison because EIS data indicate clear evidence of interaction in the former membrane, but quinacrine interaction with DOPC:Chol bilayer was inconclusive. The presence of quinacrine in the DOPC membrane is

clearly evident from SERS spectra (blue), with intense features associated with the drug at 1361 and 1538 cm^{-1} , assigned to the in-plane ring vibration and a gold surface bound exocyclic C-N band in its protonated form. The intensity of the drug Raman features indicate that it has, consistent with EIS data, successfully permeated the DOPC membrane and reached the cavity's interior, where its Raman signature is strongly SERS enhanced. When compared to its powder spectrum, the SERS spectra of quinacrine obtained from the DOPC MSLBs is redshifted, which likely indicates some adsorption at the gold cavity after its permeation. The association and permeation of quinacrine across DOPC MSLBs has little impact on the head group region (choline), from its Raman signature. Quinacrine, on the other hand, induces a blue shift band of lipidic $\delta(\text{CH}_2)$ from 1435 to 1460 cm^{-1} (Fig. 4a), as well as symmetric $\nu_s(\text{CH}_2)$ and $\nu_s(\text{CH}_3)$ which were centered at 2850 and 2906 before quinacrine blue shift to 2854 and 2908 cm^{-1} (Fig. S4, SI). This is tentatively attributed to disordering of the DOPC alkyl chain packing, which leads in the decreased resistance observed in EIS. Figure 4b illustrates the SERS spectra of DOPC:Chol MSLBs before and after quinacrine binding, along with the powder Raman spectra of DOPC, cholesterol, and quinacrine. As expected, SERS spectrum of DOPC:Chol is more complex than that of pristine DOPC spectra, with the red shift of the characteristic $\nu_s(\text{P-O})$ band at 967 cm^{-1} to 954 cm^{-1} evident indicating the interaction of cholesterol with the DOPC headgroup. The $\nu_s(\text{C-N}^+-\text{C})$ which was centered at 718 cm^{-1} in DOPC red shifts to 705 cm^{-1} in the cholesterol containing bilayer. Although the quinacrine band is detectable at the DOPC:Chol membrane, the relative intensity of the drug Raman features is dramatically lower than that observed at the DOPC MSLB (highlighted in green, Figure 4b), indicating that the drug is not reaching the cavity interior.⁷⁶ Consistent with EIS data, Raman indicates that quinacrine interaction with the membrane is restricted to the cholesterol-aromatic backbone of quinacrine within the DOPC:Chol membrane, as shown by its blue shift of the $\delta(\text{CH}_2)$ band from 1472 to 1498 cm^{-1} . Quinacrine also induces further changes that may involve membrane ordering effect of DOPC:Chol MSLBs, as reflected in $\nu_s(\text{CH}_2)$ and $\nu_s(\text{CH}_3)$ centred at 2846 and 2900 cm^{-1} respectively which is red shifted from the band observed at 2848 and 2904 cm^{-1} (Fig. S4b, SI) for pristine membrane prior to quinacrine binding. FLCS data confirms the DOPC:Chol membrane's alkyl chain ordering effect (*vide supra*).

Figure 4. Surface-enhanced Raman spectroscopy (SERS) of (a) DOPC and (b) DOPC:Chol (3:1) bilayer on a 1 μm cavity array without (black line) and with (blue line) the presence of Quinacrine (10 μM). In each panel, classical Raman spectra of DOPC, cholesterol, and quinacrine in powder form (bulk) are displayed. The regions where the SERS band position matches with conventional lipid and quinacrine bulk spectra are highlighted in grey and green respectively. Except for quinacrine powder, all spectra are presented as collected, without baseline correction.

Lifetime imaging and lipid diffusivity across MSLB upon quinacrine interaction

The effect of drugs on membrane packing and passive permeability is of particular interest since it has been proposed that a decrease in membrane order may affect membrane protein activity and protein-mediated multi drug resistance.^{85,86} To gain a better understanding of these effects, we used confocal fluorescence lifetime imaging and correlation spectroscopy to probe the influence of quinacrine on the fluidity of the DOPC, DOPC:Chol, and DOPC:SM:Chol membranes in an analogous pore-suspended membrane at an optically transparent PDMS substrate. Figure 5 shows representative reflectance and fluorescence lifetime images of the three different MSLBs comprised of DOPC, DOPC:Chol (3:1) and DOPC:SM:Chol (2:2:1)

before and after quinacrine incubation. For FLIM and FLCS measurements, fluorescent lipid marker DOPE-ATTO655 (0.01 mol%) labels the outer leaflet of the MSLBs. Before quinacrine addition, the fluorescence marker distributes equally over the pore array giving homogenous FLIM images of DOPC (Fig. 5b) and DOPC:Chol (Fig. 5e). In contrast, the FLIM image of DOPC:SM:Chol MSLB appears heterogeneous (Fig. 5h, inset), this is attributed to the expected phase separation of high melting SM and low melting DOPC lipid, and DOPE is known to show preference for liquid disordered, (L_d) phases.⁶³

Figure 5. Representative reflectance and fluorescent life-time images of MSLBs formed on a PDMS substrate. Panel a, d and g are the reflectance images of DOPC, DOPC:Chol and DOPC:SM:Chol MSLBs obtained from confocal microscopy, where the white circular spot represents an aqueous filled cavity and the black area corresponds to planar and/or unfilled cavities. Panels b, e, and h show the corresponding fluorescent life-time images of the respective bilayers before drug addition. The life-time image of bilayers are obtained from a

fluorescently labeled lipid probe, DOPE-ATTO655 (0.01mol%) present at the upper leaflet of bilayer on PDMS microcavity array. Panels c, f and i shows the respective life-time images obtained after 30 minutes of incubation with quinacrine ($\sim 10 \mu\text{M}$). The scale bar at each panel is $20\mu\text{m}$. Inset in panel (h) and (i) are the expanded regions showing a modest membrane homogenization caused by quinacrine, which is highlighted in yellow square box.

The addition of quinacrine ($10 \mu\text{M}$) had no discernible effect on the FLIM images of DOPC (Fig. 5c) and DOPC:Chol (Fig. 5f) membranes. In contrast, some modest membrane homogenization seems to occur after quinacrine incubation with DOPC:SM:Chol membrane (Fig. 5i, inset). Crucially, FLIM imaging confirms that the membranes remain intact throughout drug treatment in all instances, precluding membrane disruption as a contributor to the observed decrease in electrochemical resistance for DOPC and DOPC:SM:Chol (*vide infra*).

Next, to evaluate the impact of quinacrine interaction on membrane order, we carried out point FLCS measurements before and after quinacrine binding at these different MSLBs. Figure 6 shows representative fluorescence lifetime autocorrelation spectroscopy data acquired from the different membrane compositions; DOPC (black, Fig. 6a), DOPC:Chol (black, Fig. 6b) and DOPC:SM:Chol (black, Fig. 6c) prior to drug incubation at MSLBs. The 2D translational motion of the fluorescent lipid tracer, DOPE-ATTO655, is produced by FLCS collected from the pore center of a spanned bilayer (cf. Fig. S6 (SI)).

Figure 6. Representative FLCS autocorrelation function data obtained from different membranes such as (a) DOPC, (b) DOPC:Chol(3:1) and (c) DOPC:SM:Chol before (black open symbol) and after incubation with $10 \mu\text{M}$ quinacrine (red open symbol). The distal leaflet of all the membranes are doped with 0.01 mol% ATTO655-DOPE. The lipid membrane

spanned across the $\sim 2 \mu\text{m}$ cavity PDMS array filled with the PBS buffer, pH 7.4. In each panel, solid lines are the representative fit using the 2D diffusion model equation. At the center of pore spanning membranes of various bilayer types, at least 40-50 FLCS measurements are performed before and after drug incubation.

The lipid diffusivity was determined by fitting the ACF data to the 2D model eq. (2), as given in the experimental methods. Before drug addition, the diffusivity values for DOPC, DOPC:Chol(3:1), and DOPC:SM:Chol were calculated as $9.3\pm 0.6 \mu\text{m}^2/\text{s}$, $7.8\pm 0.3 \mu\text{m}^2/\text{s}$, and $6.2\pm 0.4 \mu\text{m}^2/\text{s}$, respectively. The data is compiled from around 40–50 measurements taken before and after drug binding for each membrane type and averaged. The trend, as expected, reflects the membrane ordering effect of cholesterol in DOPC, and the DOPC:SM:Chol(2:2:1) composition, the former is expected to contain L_d phase at room temperature and the latter contain both L_o and L_d phase. When DOPC membrane is treated with $10 \mu\text{M}$ quinacrine, the lipid diffusivity increased from 9.3 ± 0.6 to $13.03\pm 0.4 \mu\text{m}^2/\text{s}$ (Fig. 6a), indicating that the drug reduced the DOPC membrane packing. The result is consistent with the increased permittivity observed by EIS. Remarkably, in contrast, the lipid diffusivity of the DOPC:Chol (3:1) membrane decreased dramatically from $7.8\pm 0.3 \mu\text{m}^2/\text{s}$ to $0.19\pm 0.7 \mu\text{m}^2/\text{s}$ (Fig. 6b) on exposure to quinacrine. The anomalous parameter, α as defined in eq. (1), remains at 0.99 ± 0.02 before and after drug addition, suggesting that the diffusion of DOPC and DOPC:Chol(3:1) membranes are Brownian. The magnitude of reduced diffusivity at DOPC:Chol membrane seems surprising considering the drug's relatively weak impact on EIS, but it is consistent with the drug's opposing influence on this lipid composition. It implies, along with the increased resistance of the film from EIS, that drug binding may modify the phase of the DOPC:Chol membrane, we speculate that the quinacrine reduces the phase transition temperature such that it may form a gel phase at room temperature drastically reducing diffusivity. For the DOPC:SM:Chol membrane, on the other hand, consistent with DOPC data, drug induced a modest increase in lipid mobility from $6.2\pm 0.4 \mu\text{m}^2/\text{s}$ to 7.41 ± 0.25 (Fig. 5c), again associated with reduced lateral order.

Combining the aforementioned multimodal approaches, three different pore-suspended bilayers were explored here to mimic different aspects of the phases of eukaryotic cell membrane. Experiments using EIS and SERS indicated that quinacrine readily passively penetrates the DOPC bilayer, while data from fluorescence correlation and EIS reveal that this

is accompanied by increased membrane disorder and/or thinning. These alterations are irreversible, even after buffer exchange, as shown by EIS (Fig.2a, after buffer exchange).

Cholesterol had a profound impact on permeation through the Ld phase membrane. When incorporated at 30% mol/mol in a DOPC bilayer, quinacrine permeation was blocked, as confirmed by SERS studies. These observations are in line with previous findings that cholesterol reduces passive uptake of different classes of drugs^{87,88} as well as biomimetic gold nanoparticles⁸⁹. Correspondingly, the drug had only modest impact on membrane resistance where it was observed in contrast to DOPC alone to stimulate a small increase in resistance and (Fig. 3a) a decrease in capacitance (Table 2 and Fig. 3b). At higher quinacrine concentrations drug intercalation may thicken the membrane, consistent with a prior study.⁹⁰ From SERS, alkyl chain symmetric CH₂ stretching bands indicated also that quinacrine binding impacted membrane ordering (Fig. S4, SI). Small molecules may enhance the overall packing of the alkyl chain by orienting the P⁻-N⁺ dipole of the lipid headgroup.⁹¹ Furthermore, remarkably, the lipid diffusivity measurements by FLCS revealed lipid alkyl chain ordering (Fig. 6b) with a massive decrease in membrane diffusivity evident on exposure of the binary membrane to the drug. Since DOPC:Chol (3:1) is not expected to exhibit any domains or phase separation at room temperature^{65,92}, the severe decrease in lipid diffusivity due to quinacrine binding is speculated to be due to gel-like domains within DOPC:Chol membrane caused by the drug.

Using an empirical binding model, there is a modest ($K_a = 0.23 \pm 0.07 \text{ L. } \mu\text{M}^{-1}$) affinity between quinacrine and DOPC:Chol membrane, however, the affinity between DOPC and quinacrine is much higher ($K_a = 1.27 \pm 0.016 \text{ L. } \mu\text{M}^{-1}$). Although, these values are empirical they may explain the stated inhibitory value for lysosomal phospholipase, a mode of action suggested for antimalarial drugs.^{29,93}

Compared to DOPC, DOPC:SM:Chol (1:1:0.5), which is a closer analogue of the eukaryotic plasma membrane, showed the largest drop in resistance and a low K_a ($0.30 \pm 0.011 \text{ L. } \mu\text{M}^{-1}$) on drug contact. The resistance values indicate the drug increases membrane admittance possibly by reducing packing order of SM-Chol rich regions, resulting in ion leakage. We observed (Fig. 3b) an increase in capacitance, indicating membrane thinning. At room temperature ($22 \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$), a membrane composed of DOPC, SM, Chol (1:1:0.5) is expected to form phase separated domains, of liquid disordered and ordered phase rich in cholesterol.^{63,94} Given that we observed a greater increase in resistance and a decrease in than the Ld

membranes. We hypothesize that quinacrine treatment may increase cholesterol redistribution (lipidosis) in SM-Chol rich regions, increasing membrane disorder. Our SERS data are consistent with this. For instance, in the absence of quinacrine, the band centered at 1635 cm^{-1} (Fig. S5, highlighted in red, SI) is formed by intramolecular H-bonding interaction between SM amide I (C=O) and cholesterol -OH group, which is redshifted from 1643 cm^{-1} due to SM-SM H-bond.⁹⁵ In the presence of quinacrine, 1642 cm^{-1} band reappears, indicating quinacrine interacts with SM headgroup by dislodging cholesterol from the region of SM. Our results are in line with the previous report, which found that quinacrine abolishes prion protein activity by redistributing cholesterol from the plasma membrane to intracellular membranes, thereby destabilizing membrane domain.⁹⁶

Reorganization of the lipid bilayer may potentially affect drug-protein and membrane-protein interactions.⁹⁷ Quinacrine induces membrane heterogeneity ($\Delta m = -ve$) at DOPC:SM:Chol membrane, but not at DOPC and DOPC:Chol membrane ($\Delta m \approx 0$), according to our EIS data (cf. Fig. S7, SI), which was further corroborated using FLIM imaging. The exponent of CPE values (m) often defines the overall homogeneity of the membrane.^{55,98}

Overall, the study shows the versatility of MSLBs as platforms to interrogate drug-membrane interaction, though of course, one disadvantage of this and other model membranes is that they do not reflect the true complexity of the plasma membrane; lacking protein and other features such as glycocalyx, it only reflects lipid membrane interaction and passive permeation; however, because passive permeation can be difficult to establish in cells, it is useful in this regard.

Conclusions

We interrogated lipid membrane interactions and permeability of multi purpose drug quinacrine at microcavity array supported lipid bilayers of different compositions. The membrane three compositions were selected to reflect membrane phases present at the cell membrane, liquid disordered, with and without cholesterol and mixed L_o/L_d phases. The impact of cholesterol and phase heterogeneity induced by mixed lipid composition on quinacrine-membrane interaction and permeability was evaluated using electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) and surface enhanced Raman spectroscopy (SERS) in label free studies and

the fluidity of the membrane in response to drug was evaluated by fluorescence lifetime correlation spectroscopy.

EIS data reveals the drug is permeable toward DOPC and the ternary DOPC:SM:Chol compositions. It reduces membrane resistance and increases impedance in both cases. For the ternary membrane the impact is greatest indicating possible reorganisation of lipid domains as reflected by decrease in admittance of membrane. Conversely permeation is arrested at the cholesterol/DOPC membrane but the drug binds/intercalates at membrane interface making it more resistant to ion permeation as reflected in non-Faradaic impedance in an increase in admittance of the membrane. SERS confirmed membrane binding in the binary composition without permeation. While exploiting SERS to monitor arrival of drug at the plasmonic pore, we could unequivocally confirm membrane permeation for the primary and ternary compositions. Confocal fluorescent lifetime imaging (FLIM) confirmed that membranes remained intact during and after drug interaction, and fluorescence correlation spectroscopy (FLCS) showed that DOPC and ternary membranes undergo increased lipid diffusivity on drug binding, whereas the fluidity of the DOPC:Chol membrane decreases dramatically with drug interaction, which is speculated to be due to lowering in gel phase transition temperature.

Overall, the study shed light not only on the role of physical properties of the membrane in the interaction of antimalarial drugs, but demonstrates that MSLB platforms holds great promise for screening passive permeability of drug across different biomembranes and can be extended to various other receptors such as enzyme, toxins, and protein mediated transport across the biomembrane.

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Supporting Information

Pore-suspended bilayer fabrication, additional results from EIS, computational calculations, and SERS, etc are provided.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare no conflicting of interest.

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